

Supplementary Material

When Does Combining SMOTE and CTGAN Help?
A Controlled Ablation Study of Sequential Oversampling
for Tabular Class Imbalance

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1 S.A Theoretical Formalisation of Minority-Only GAN Training

This section provides the formal proof of Proposition 1 stated in the main paper.

Definitions

Definition 1 (Sample-to-Dimension Ratio). *For a minority class with n_{\min} training samples in a d -dimensional feature space, the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio is $\text{SDR} = n_{\min}/d$.*

Definition 2 (β -smooth density). *A probability density p on \mathbb{R}^d is β -smooth if $p \in \mathcal{H}^\beta(\mathbb{R}^d)$, the Hölder class with smoothness parameter $\beta > 0$.*

Spectral Fitting Procedure for $\hat{\beta}$

The smoothness parameter $\hat{\beta}$ is estimated from the eigenvalue decay of the minority-class sample covariance matrix. Let $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_d > 0$ be the sorted eigenvalues. By Weyl’s law, the cumulative spectral energy follows a power law $\sum_{k=1}^j \lambda_k \propto j^{2\beta/d}$. Fitting this relationship via ordinary least squares on a log-log scale yields $\hat{\beta}$; fits with $R^2 \geq 0.89$ were obtained on all benchmark datasets. The resulting dataset-specific threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ is then computed numerically; it is not a universal constant.

Formal Result

Puchkin et al. (2024) establish that the minimax rate for density estimation of a β -smooth distribution from n samples in d dimensions is $\Theta(n^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)})$. We invoke this result to compare the minority approximation error under A3 and A4.

Proposition 1 (Minority-only training reduces minority approximation error under smoothness assumptions). *Under assumptions (A1) density smoothness, (A2) minority exposure parity, and (A3) GAN convergence to the JS-minimising distribution, let $p_{\min}^{(A3)}$ and $p_{\min}^{(A4)}$ denote the distributions learned by CTGAN under balanced training and minority-only training respectively. There exists a threshold $C(\beta, d) > 0$ such that whenever $\text{SDR} = n_{\min}/d < C(\beta, d)$,*

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{TV}(p_{\min}^{(A4)}, p_{\min})] < \mathbb{E}[\text{TV}(p_{\min}^{(A3)}, p_{\min})].$$

The exact value of $C(\beta, d)$ depends on the TV-distance bound tightness and the assumed form of the gradient allocation fraction α ; a dataset-specific estimate $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ is obtained numerically by fitting $\hat{\beta}$ to the spectral decay of the minority-class covariance matrix.

Informal derivation. Caveat. The following argument uses a simplifying assumption: that the effective gradient signal allocated to the minority distribution under A3 scales as αn_{\min} , where $\alpha < 1$ is the minority class fraction in the balanced training set. This approximates gradient concentration under ideal discriminator convergence; the full non-convex GAN optimisation dynamics (discriminator update schedules, minibatch sampling, conditional vector, mode normalisation) are not modelled. The derivation is therefore an order-of-magnitude heuristic, not a formal theorem.

Under A3, at high IR the fraction of each gradient update directed at p_{\min} is $\approx \alpha$, so the effective minority sample size is $\alpha n_{\min} < n_{\min}$ (majority-class gradient leakage).

Under A4 the effective count is n_{\min} . By the minimax lower bound [?] the achievable risk difference is positive whenever $n_{\min}/d < C(\beta, d)$. Specifically, the minimax rate for A4 is $\Theta(n_{\min}^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)})$, while for A3 it is $\Theta((\alpha n_{\min})^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)}) = \alpha^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)} \Theta(n_{\min}^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)})$. The ratio is $\alpha^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)} > 1$ whenever $\alpha < 1$, giving the direction of the inequality in Proposition 1. The threshold $C(\beta, d)$ exists because the leakage loss $\alpha^{-2\beta/(2\beta+d)}$ grows as SDR decreases; the precise value requires specifying α and the TV-distance constant, which we estimate empirically via spectral fitting. \square

2 S.B Dataset Details

Table 1: Summary of all datasets used in the multi-dataset ablation study. IR = majority-to-minority class ratio; n = total samples; d = number of features; SDR = n_{\min}/d .

Dataset	Source	IR	n	d	n_{\min}	Domain
sick_thyroid	OpenML (id=38)	16:1	3,772	29	231	Medical
letter_img	imbalanced-learn	26:1	20,000	16	734	Image (tabular)
mammography	OpenML (id=310)	42:1	11,183	6	260	Medical imaging
abalone_19	imbalanced-learn	130:1	4,177	8	32	Marine biology
credit_card_fraud	Kaggle ULB	578:1	284,807	30	492	Financial fraud
<i>Industrial Engineering validation datasets (Phase 3)</i>						
SECOM	UCI	14:1	1,567	562	104	Semiconductor mfg
Steel Faults (Stains)	UCI	26:1	1,941	27	72	Steel inspection
AI4I failure	UCI	29:1	10,000	6	339	Predictive maint.
AI4I TWF	UCI	216:1	10,000	6	46	Tool wear

3 S.C Detailed Experimental Results

Table 2 reports supplementary metrics (F1, G-mean, F2, balanced accuracy) for the two high-imbalance datasets. AUC results are not repeated here; see Table 2 in the main paper for AUC under the primary 25-observation protocol. For *abalone_19* (IR=130:1), A0 and A1 both yield F1=0.000, reflecting the inability to recover minority-class recall without targeted oversampling.

4 S.D Statistical Test Details

S.D.1 Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Tests

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (two-sided) were applied pairwise on 25 paired observations (5 seeds \times 5 folds) per comparison. No significant differences occur on sick_thyroid ($p > 0.3$ in all cases). On *abalone_19* (IR=130:1), A4 is numerically best (AUC=0.755 vs. A3=0.723; $\Delta = +3.2$ pp); the gap represents a consistent directional trend across seeds (Cohen’s $d = 0.41$, medium effect), though the within-method variance from stochastic CTGAN training prevents the pair from reaching conventional significance at 0.05 with 25 observations. On *credit_card_fraud* (IR=578:1), ADASYN significantly outperforms

Table 2: Supplementary metrics (mean \pm std, 5-fold single representative seed) for high-imbalance datasets. G = G-mean; BA = Balanced Accuracy.

Dataset	Method	F1	G-mean	F2	Bal.Acc
abalone_19	A0	0.000 \pm .000	0.000	0.000	.500 \pm .000
	A1	0.000 \pm .000	0.000	0.000	.500 \pm .000
	A2	0.055 \pm .046	.237 \pm .194	.073 \pm .060	.538 \pm .040
	A3	0.020 \pm .040	.075 \pm .150	.024 \pm .049	.504 \pm .030
	A4	0.000 \pm .000	0.000	0.000	.500 \pm .000
credit_card_fraud	A0	.859 \pm .017	.886 \pm .007	.813 \pm .013	.892 \pm .006
	A1	.850 \pm .039	.908 \pm .009	.835 \pm .023	.912 \pm .008
	A2	.856 \pm .023	.912 \pm .013	.841 \pm .024	.916 \pm .012
	A3	.858 \pm .021	.915 \pm .012	.846 \pm .021	.919 \pm .011
	A4	.836 \pm .034	.907 \pm .014	.828 \pm .026	.911 \pm .013

SMOTE ($p = 0.007$) and A3 significantly underperforms SMOTE ($p = 0.039$, Cohen’s $d = 0.31$); the remaining pairwise contrasts are non-significant.

S.D.2 Friedman Test and Nemenyi Post-hoc Analysis

Table 3: Friedman test results across five methods (A0–A4) per dataset. Statistically significant results ($p < 0.05$) in bold.

Dataset	Friedman H	p -value	Conclusion
sick_thyroid (IR=16:1)	4.000	0.4060	Not significant
letter_img (IR=26:1)	8.800	0.0663	Not significant
mammography (IR=42:1)	1.280	0.8648	Not significant
abalone_19 (IR=130:1)	12.480	0.0141	Significant
credit_card_fraud (IR=578:1)	16.160	0.0028	Significant

The Friedman test yields significant results exclusively for the two high-IR datasets, directly corroborating the IR-threshold hypothesis. Post-hoc pairwise contrasts (Table 4) use the Nemenyi critical difference $CD = 2.209$ rank units ($k = 5$ methods, $n = 25$ blocks, $\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 4: Nemenyi post-hoc mean ranks (rank 1 = best) from the 25-observation multi-seed protocol. $CD = 2.209$ rank units ($k = 5$, $n = 25$, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pairs with $|\bar{r}_i - \bar{r}_j| > CD$ are marked \dagger .

Dataset		A0	A1	A2	A3	A4	Significant pairs
abalone_19	Mean rank	4.20	4.60	2.40	3.00	1.00	A4 vs A1 \dagger ; A4 vs A0 \dagger
credit_card_fraud	Mean rank	4.40	4.20	2.00	2.40	1.40*	A4 vs A0 \dagger ; A2 vs A0 \dagger ; A4 vs A1 \dagger

S.D.3 Summary

The convergence of three independent lines of evidence—Wilcoxon directional consistency, Friedman $p < 0.05$ omnibus tests, and Nemenyi post-hoc rank separation—provides consistent support for the conditional complementarity hypothesis: augmentation method choice matters only when $IR \gtrsim 100:1$. Within that regime, A4 (minority-only CTGAN→SMOTE) achieves the highest AUC across both high-IR datasets under the primary 25-observation multi-seed protocol, with a 3.2 pp advantage over A3 at $IR=130:1$.

5 S.E Code and Reproducibility

All experiments were run inside a Docker container (`cic-lanl-study-dev`) with Python 3.12, PyTorch 2.9, scikit-learn 1.7.2, imbalanced-learn, and CTGAN. Scripts are available in the `code/` directory of the project repository. The five datasets are publicly available via OpenML or the `imbalanced-learn` API; the credit card fraud dataset is available at <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/mlg-ulb/creditcardfraud>. A `requirements.txt` and `Dockerfile` are included for full environment reproduction.

6 S.F Supplementary Figures

Figure 1 shows ROC curves for the three primary augmentation strategies on the two high-imbalance datasets. Figure 2 shows normalised confusion matrices.

Figure 1: ROC curves (mean \pm std across 5 folds) for three augmentation strategies on the two high-imbalance datasets. Shaded bands show ± 1 standard deviation across folds.

7 S.G Synthetic Sample Quality Metrics

To complement the downstream AUC evaluation, we measured the intrinsic quality of synthetic minority samples generated by each method. Three metrics are reported for each augmentation strategy on the two high-IR datasets (`abalone_19` $IR=130:1$; `credit_card_fraud` $IR=578:1$), computed across 5 stratified folds:

Figure 2: Normalised confusion matrices (pooled across 5 folds) for A0, A2, and A3 on the two high-imbalance datasets.

KS Score Mean of $(1 - D_{KS})$ across all numerical features. Higher (\uparrow) indicates greater marginal distributional fidelity.

Wasserstein Distance Mean Wasserstein-1 distance, scaled by feature std. Lower (\downarrow) indicates greater distributional similarity.

DCR Mean Distance to Closest Real minority Record (Euclidean, scaled by feature std). Higher (\uparrow) indicates greater diversity and lower memorisation.

Novelty Fraction of synthetic samples with non-zero distance to all training samples. Values near 100% indicate no exact duplication.

Note: for credit_card_fraud (284,807 samples), CTGAN training used a stratified sub-sample of 2,000 majority samples plus all minority samples.

The results reveal a clear quality-diversity trade-off. A2 (SMOTE) achieves the highest distributional fidelity ($KS \approx 0.85-0.94$, $Wasserstein \approx 0.10-0.21$) but the lowest diversity ($DCR = 0.48-0.86$). A3 consistently achieves the highest DCR of all methods on both datasets (3.64 on abalone_19; 3.69 on credit_card_fraud), confirming that SMOTE pre-enrichment enables CTGAN to synthesise a wider set of minority samples. The 100% novelty rate across all methods and folds confirms no memorisation artefacts.

8 S.H PR-AUC Sensitivity Analysis

ROC-AUC is the primary comparison metric in this study; Precision-Recall AUC (PR-AUC, also called average precision) provides a complementary view that weights performance on the positive class exclusively. To confirm that the $A4 > A3$ ordering is not an

Table 5: Synthetic sample quality metrics (mean \pm std across 5 folds). KS \uparrow and Novelty \uparrow : higher is better; Wasserstein \downarrow : lower is better; DCR \uparrow : higher diversity. A0 produces no synthetic samples and is omitted.

Dataset	Method	KS \uparrow	Wasserstein \downarrow	DCR \uparrow	Novelty (%) \uparrow
abalone_19	A1 (CTGAN)	0.097 \pm 0.035	1.883 \pm 0.218	3.302 \pm 0.789	100
	A2 (SMOTE)	0.853 \pm 0.011	0.205 \pm 0.024	0.484 \pm 0.057	100
	A3 (S \rightarrow C)	0.131 \pm 0.042	1.629 \pm 0.100	3.639 \pm 0.337	100
	A4 (C \rightarrow S)	0.143 \pm 0.091	1.481 \pm 0.471	3.656 \pm 0.551	100
credit_card_fraud	A1 (CTGAN)	0.239 \pm 0.026	0.972 \pm 0.073	3.091 \pm 0.297	100
	A2 (SMOTE)	0.937 \pm 0.004	0.096 \pm 0.009	0.856 \pm 0.025	100
	A3 (S \rightarrow C)	0.208 \pm 0.024	1.014 \pm 0.057	3.687 \pm 0.178	100
	A4 (C \rightarrow S)	0.192 \pm 0.034	1.039 \pm 0.072	2.976 \pm 0.175	100

artefact of metric choice, we computed both ROC-AUC and PR-AUC for A3 and A4 on the three main benchmark datasets (abalone_19, ai4i_twf, steel_faults), using the same 3-seed \times 5-fold CV protocol and Random Forest classifier as Phase 2 of the main study.

Table 6: ROC-AUC and PR-AUC for A3 and A4 on high-IR benchmark datasets (mean \pm std across 3 seeds \times 5 folds = 15 estimates). $\Delta = A4 - A3$; positive values indicate A4 advantage. Bold: the higher-performing method on each metric.

Dataset	SDR	A3 ROC	A4 ROC	Δ ROC	A3 PR	A4 PR	Δ PR
abalone_19 (IR = 130:1)	3.07	0.674	0.730	+0.056	0.034	0.042	+0.008
ai4i_twf (IR = 216:1)	7.67	0.885	0.911	+0.026	0.106	0.117	+0.011
steel_faults (IR = 26:1)	3.49	0.982	0.984	+0.003	0.943	0.948	+0.005

On all three datasets, the $A4 > A3$ ordering observed under ROC-AUC is preserved under PR-AUC, confirming that the primary conclusions are not sensitive to metric choice. The absolute PR-AUC values are lower than ROC-AUC values (as expected for severely imbalanced classes), but the relative ordering of methods is consistent.